

Evaluating Traditional and Ensemble Learning Techniques for Churn Prediction

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Abstract—Customer churn prediction is a critical problem in industries where retaining users is more cost-effective than acquiring new ones. This paper explores and compares the performance of several foundational machine learning techniques for churn detection using a publicly available telecom dataset. The dataset is preprocessed through feature selection, encoding, scaling, and handling of missing values to ensure robustness. We evaluate multiple classifiers, including Logistic Regression, Support Vector Machines (SVM), Decision Trees, Random Forest, Gradient Boosting, and ensemble models such as AdaBoost, XGBoost, CatBoost, and Naive Bayes. In addition to individual model evaluation using metrics like accuracy, precision, recall, F1-score, ROC-AUC, and the Kolmogorov–Smirnov (KS) statistic, we propose a stacking ensemble classifier that combines the predictive capabilities of diverse base learners. The stacking model leverages Random Forest, Decision Tree, Support Vector Machine, and CatBoost classifiers, with Logistic Regression as a meta-learner. Our experiments show that ensemble learning, particularly stacking, outperforms individual classifiers in terms of predictive accuracy and class separation, offering a more effective approach to identifying high-risk churn customers.

Index Terms—Customer churn, machine learning, ensemble learning, stacking classifier, churn prediction, classification models.

I. INTRODUCTION

In highly competitive industries such as telecommunications, customer retention is a key driver of long-term profitability. The cost of acquiring new customers often exceeds that of retaining existing ones, making churn prediction a critical task for business intelligence and strategic planning. Customer churn refers to the phenomenon where customers discontinue their relationship with a service provider. Early identification of such customers enables businesses to implement targeted retention strategies, potentially saving substantial revenue.

With the growing availability of customer data, machine learning (ML) has emerged as a powerful tool for churn prediction. Unlike traditional statistical models, machine learning algorithms can learn complex, nonlinear patterns in high-dimensional data and generalize well to unseen instances. Numerous techniques—including tree-based models [1], support vector machines [2], and ensemble learners [3]—have been successfully applied in past research to predict churn behavior. However, the performance of these models varies significantly depending on dataset characteristics, feature engineering, and model configuration.

This paper explores a range of foundational machine learning algorithms for the task of churn prediction using a structured telecommunications dataset. We systematically evaluate each model’s predictive performance using classification metrics such as accuracy, precision, recall, F1-score, ROC-AUC, and the Kolmogorov–Smirnov (KS) statistic. In addition, we propose a stacking ensemble classifier that integrates multiple base learners—Random Forest, Decision Tree, Support Vector Machine, and CatBoost—into a unified model, with Logistic Regression serving as the meta-learner. Our objective is twofold:

- To benchmark various classification techniques in the context of churn detection
- To demonstrate the effectiveness of ensemble methods, particularly stacking, in enhancing predictive accuracy and robustness. Through this comparative analysis, we aim to provide practical insights into model selection and deployment for churn analytics in customer-centric industries.

II. RELATED WORKS

Customer churn prediction has long been a focus of marketing and data science research, particularly in subscription-based industries such as telecommunications. Early foundational work by Neslin et al. [4] emphasized the importance of model interpretability and predictive accuracy, setting a benchmark for evaluating churn models. Their study underscored the need for reliable predictive frameworks grounded in behavioral data.

Building on this foundation, Idris et al. [5] explored intelligent churn prediction using ensemble learning with mRMR feature selection and RotBoost, demonstrating the effectiveness of boosting methods in handling large feature spaces. Similarly, Amin et al. [6] adopted a rough set approach to address the vagueness inherent in churn data, highlighting the usefulness of soft computing techniques in real-world telecom environments.

One significant challenge in churn modeling is class imbalance, where churned customers represent a minority. Burez and Van den Poel [7] proposed techniques to mitigate this issue, such as resampling strategies, to enhance classifier performance. More recently, Ahmad et al. [8] employed scalable machine learning methods in a big data context, showing that

distributed platforms like Spark can significantly improve both training time and model accuracy.

CatBoost, a gradient boosting technique optimized for categorical features, has also been effectively applied in recent studies. Angelina et al. [9] demonstrated its superior performance in predicting churn in telecom using real-world datasets, validating its strength over traditional methods. Other gradient boosting frameworks like LightGBM and XGBoost have also been extensively evaluated. Zhang and Gong [10] compared these models in healthcare prediction and found LightGBM to offer a strong balance between speed and accuracy, insights which are transferable to churn tasks.

Deep learning has also made inroads into churn prediction. Fujo et al. [11] implemented a deep neural network approach in the telecom industry, revealing its potential in capturing nonlinear feature interactions, although at the cost of interpretability. Ensemble methods continue to show robust performance across domains. Coussement and De Bock [3] applied ensemble models in the online gambling industry and reported improved accuracy and resilience to overfitting.

Most recently, Xu et al. [12] proposed a feature grouping-based ensemble framework for telecom churn, combining multiple base learners to further enhance generalizability.

III. EXPLORATORY DATA ANALYSIS

A exploratory data analysis (EDA) was conducted to understand customer behavior and identify patterns correlated with churn. This step provided insights that informed feature selection and modeling decisions.

Contract type emerged as a strong indicator of churn behavior. As shown in Fig.1, customers on month-to-month contracts account for a disproportionately high number of churn cases, while those on one-year and two-year contracts tend to remain with the company. This is expected, as long-term contracts may introduce a commitment or early termination cost that discourages cancellation. In terms of payment

Fig. 1. Churn by contract type. Month-to-month contracts show higher churn. method, approximately 39% of customers use credit cards,

making it the 2nd most common mode of payment behind bank withdrawals (Fig.2). While not a direct churn driver, understanding payment preferences is valuable for customer profiling and targeted engagement.

Payment Method Distribution

Fig. 2. Distribution of payment methods.

Analysis of the Senior Citizen demographic (Fig.3) revealed that senior citizens are less likely to churn compared to younger customers. This suggests age or lifestyle stability could be associated with higher retention.

Churn Distribution by Senior Citizen Status

Fig. 3. Churn by senior citizen status. Seniors churn less.

The tenure distribution (Fig.4) shows a bimodal pattern. A large segment of customers have been with the company for 0–5 months, possibly reflecting trial users or new signups. Another significant group has tenures in the 65–70 month range, indicating long-term loyal users.

The total charges distribution (Fig.5) is right-skewed, with most customers falling within the \$0–\$1000 range. There is a sharp decline in customer count as total charges increase,

Fig. 4. Tenure distribution. Peaks at 0–5 and 65–70 months.

possibly due to fewer customers staying for extended periods or subscribing to premium plans.

Fig. 5. Distribution of total charges. Most customers fall below \$1000.

Analysis of the monthly charge distribution (Fig.6) shows that most customers are billed under \$100 per month, with the frequency tapering off as charges increase. This right-skewed pattern suggests that lower-tier service plans are more common, while higher charges are relatively rare. Understanding this distribution is important, as subsequent analysis indicates that customers with higher monthly charges are more likely to churn.

Fig. 6. Distribution of monthly charges. Most values are below \$100.

A more focused view is provided by the KDE plot in Fig.7, which compares monthly charges between churned and non-churned customers. Customers with low monthly charges tend to remain, whereas those with higher monthly charges are more likely to churn. This may suggest dissatisfaction with service value at higher price points.

Further analysis of customer tenure in months (Fig.8) reveals a clear relationship with churn behavior. Customers with short tenures, particularly those in their first few months, exhibit a significantly higher likelihood of churn. In contrast, customers with longer tenures—typically those who have stayed with the company for over a year—are markedly more

Fig. 7. Monthly charges by churn. High charges linked to churn.

stable and less prone to churn. This suggests that the early lifecycle of a customer is a critical churn window, and targeted interventions during this period may help improve retention rates.

Fig. 8. Tenure by churn. Short-tenure customers churn more.

These EDA findings not only reveal meaningful relationships but also underscore the importance of features like contract type, tenure, and monthly charges in building a predictive churn model.

IV. METHODOLOGY

This section outlines the approach adopted for building and evaluating machine learning models for customer churn prediction. The methodology involves multiple stages: data preprocessing, feature engineering, model development, and evaluation using various performance metrics. The full pipeline is designed to ensure a fair and reproducible comparison across multiple classification techniques.

A. Dataset Description

The dataset used in this study is the Telco Customer Churn dataset, originally distributed as a sample within IBM Cognos Analytics. It simulates customer data for a fictional telecommunications company, comprising approximately 7,000 records and 49 attributes. The features span customer demographics, service subscriptions, account information, and usage metrics. The target variable is binary, indicating whether a customer has churned ($Churn = 1$) or stayed ($Churn = 0$).

B. Data Preprocessing

The raw dataset required several preprocessing steps:

- **Handling Missing Values:** Missing entries in categorical fields such as *Internet Type* were imputed with a placeholder value "No" to indicate the absence of service.
- **Feature Selection:** Redundant or leakage-prone features such as *Customer ID*, *Zip Code*, and *Total Revenue* were removed. Feature importance and correlation analysis were used to retain the most informative predictors.
- **Encoding Categorical Features:** All non-numeric fields were converted using one-hot encoding or label encoding, as appropriate.
- **Feature Scaling:** To ensure that models sensitive to feature magnitude (e.g., SVM, logistic regression) performed optimally, numerical features were standardized using *StandardScaler*.

To better understand feature relationships and identify potential multicollinearity, a correlation matrix was computed and visualized as a heatmap. This helped in refining the feature selection process and informed decisions on removing redundant or highly correlated attributes. Fig.9 shows the correlation between selected numerical features, with notable associations observed between total charges, tenure, and monthly charges.

Fig. 9. Correlation heatmap showing pairwise relationships among features.

C. Model Development

Multiple classification models were trained on the preprocessed dataset. These include:

- **Baseline Models:** Logistic Regression, Decision Tree, Random Forest, Support Vector Machine (SVM), Naive Bayes, and K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN).
- **Ensemble Models:** AdaBoost, Gradient Boosting, XGBoost, and CatBoost.
- **Stacking Ensemble:** A stacking classifier was constructed using four base learners—Random Forest, Decision Tree,

SVM (with scaling pipeline), and CatBoost—with Logistic Regression as the meta-learner. The ensemble was trained using 5-fold cross-validation to avoid overfitting and to leverage complementary strengths of each model.

D. Feature Engineering Techniques

To improve model performance and interpretability:

- **L1 Regularization:** Logistic regression with L1 penalty was used to perform embedded feature selection.
- **Permutation Importance:** Post-training, permutation importance was applied to assess the relative contribution of features to each model's predictive power.

E. Evaluation Metrics

Each model was evaluated using multiple metrics to gain a comprehensive view of performance:

- **Accuracy:** The proportion of correct predictions.
- **Precision, Recall, and F1-Score:** To evaluate the model's ability to detect churners, especially under class imbalance.
- **ROC-AUC Score:** Measures the area under the receiver operating characteristic curve.
- **Confusion Matrix:** Visualizes true positives, false positives, true negatives, and false negatives.
- **Kolmogorov–Smirnov (KS) Statistic:** Used to evaluate the separation power of the model between the positive and negative class distributions, particularly relevant for churn modeling.

F. Experimental Setup

All experiments were conducted using Python 3.12 on a machine with an Apple M2 processor, 8GB RAM, running macOS 15.4. The following open-source libraries were used: scikit-learn 1.6.1, XGBoost 3.0.0, CatBoost 1.2.8, pandas 2.2.3, numpy 1.26.4, seaborn 0.13.2, matplotlib 3.10.11 for visualization. All models were implemented using scikit-learn, with the exception of XGBoost and CatBoost, which used their respective native libraries.

The dataset was split into 80% training and 20% testing sets, with a fixed random seed (42) to ensure reproducibility across experiments. Where applicable, 5-fold stratified cross-validation was employed to evaluate model stability.

Hyperparameters for tree-based models were tuned empirically, with typical settings including `n_estimators=100`, `max_depth=8`, and `learning_rate=0.1`. For SVM and Logistic Regression, numerical features were standardized using *StandardScaler*, and pipelines were constructed to ensure preprocessing was integrated into training. The stacking ensemble combined four base learners—Random Forest, Decision Tree, SVM, and CatBoost—with Logistic Regression as the meta-learner.

The experimental setup was designed to ensure fair and consistent evaluation of all models under comparable conditions.

V. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section presents the evaluation results of various machine learning models used for customer churn prediction, followed by a discussion of key findings and feature importance insights.

A. Model Performance Comparison

Table I and Table II summarize the performance of the models evaluated in this study across six metrics: accuracy, precision, recall, F1-score, ROC-AUC, and the Kolmogorov–Smirnov (KS) statistic.

TABLE I
MODEL PERFORMANCE: ACCURACY, PRECISION, RECALL, AND F1 SCORE

Model	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1 Score
CatBoost	0.8517	0.7741	0.6230	0.6904
Gradient Boosting	0.8474	0.7573	0.6257	0.6852
XGBoost	0.8439	0.7421	0.6310	0.6821
Random Forest	0.8410	0.7534	0.5963	0.6657
AdaBoost	0.8282	0.6919	0.6364	0.6630
Stacking Classifier	0.8502	0.7700	0.6200	0.6900
Naive Bayes	0.7551	0.5256	0.7968	0.6334
Logistic Regression	0.7814	0.5943	0.5562	0.5746
Decision Tree	0.7807	0.5921	0.5588	0.5750
SVM	0.7835	0.7482	0.2781	0.4055
KNN	0.7786	0.6598	0.3422	0.4507

TABLE II
MODEL PERFORMANCE: AUC AND KS STATISTIC

Model	AUC	KS Statistic
CatBoost	0.91	0.6812
Gradient Boosting	0.91	0.6887
XGBoost	0.90	0.6323
Random Forest	0.90	0.6550
AdaBoost	0.90	0.6509
Stacking Classifier	0.91	0.6812
Naive Bayes	0.85	0.5518
Logistic Regression	0.81	0.4584
Decision Tree	0.71	0.4197
SVM	0.81	0.4910
KNN	0.74	0.3641

Among all individual models, CatBoost achieved the highest accuracy (85.2%) and tied for the best ROC-AUC score (0.91), indicating strong discriminative ability. It also had a competitive F1-score (0.690) and KS statistic (0.6812), demonstrating its capability to separate churners from non-churners effectively. Gradient Boosting followed closely, with a slightly lower accuracy but the highest KS statistic (0.6887), suggesting strong class separation. XGBoost also performed well across most metrics, showing robustness and consistency.

The Stacking Classifier, which combines CatBoost, Random Forest, Decision Tree, and SVM as base learners with Logistic Regression as a meta-learner, achieved comparable performance to CatBoost with an accuracy of 85.04%, AUC of 0.91, and KS of 0.6812. This supports the hypothesis that combining multiple models can capture complementary patterns in the data and improve generalization.

Fig. 10. Confusion matrix for CatBoost classifier predictions on the test set.

Fig. 11. Kolmogorov–Smirnov (KS) curve illustrating class separation for the CatBoost classifier.

In contrast, simpler models like Naive Bayes, Logistic Regression, and Decision Tree achieved lower accuracy and AUC values, although Naive Bayes had a high recall (0.797), meaning it was better at identifying churners but at the cost of precision. SVM and KNN suffered from low recall, leading to poor F1-scores despite decent accuracy.

B. Feature Importance Analysis

To understand what drives churn in the dataset, permutation importance and tree-based feature evaluation were conducted. The most influential features are listed in Table III.

The Contract type emerged as the most important feature, which aligns with domain intuition: customers with month-to-

Fig. 12. ROC-AUC curves comparing the performance of all classifiers.

TABLE III
TOP 10 FEATURES BY IMPORTANCE

Rank	Feature	Importance
1	Contract	0.0762
2	Number of Referrals	0.0353
3	Tenure in Months	0.0286
4	Monthly Charge	0.0166
5	Age	0.0083
6	Total Charges	0.0076
7	Senior Citizen	0.0072
8	Number of Dependents	0.0065
9	Payment Method	0.0065
10	Streaming Music	0.0057

month contracts are more likely to churn compared to those in long-term plans. Tenure, monthly charges, and referral count also significantly influenced churn, suggesting that loyalty and engagement play a key role in retention. Interestingly, Streaming Music and Payment Method also contributed, hinting at the role of service experience and billing preferences.

To further investigate the influence of individual features on model predictions, we analyzed feature importance across three representative models: Logistic Regression, Random Forest, and XGBoost. These models offer complementary perspectives—Logistic Regression provides linear coefficients that reflect the direct impact of features, while Random Forest and XGBoost use tree-based mechanisms to evaluate the reduction in impurity or information gain. Fig.13, 14, and 15 respectively visualize the top contributing features identified by each model. This comparative analysis highlights consistent patterns in feature relevance—such as the prominence of contract type and tenure—while also revealing model-specific differences in how features are weighted.

C. Discussion

The results highlight that ensemble models consistently outperform individual learners, particularly gradient boosting and stacking methods. CatBoost and the stacking ensemble both offer a high-performance, generalizable approach to churn prediction, while maintaining reasonable interpretability.

Fig. 13. Top features ranked by coefficient magnitude in Logistic Regression.

Fig. 14. Feature importance scores based on impurity reduction in Random Forest.

The analysis also confirms that churn is a multi-faceted behavior, influenced by contractual, financial, demographic, and behavioral factors. These insights can help telecom providers design targeted interventions for at-risk customers.

VI. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

In this study, we explored and evaluated a broad range of machine learning techniques for the task of customer churn prediction using a structured telecom dataset. Through

Fig. 15. XGBoost feature importance based on gain (information contribution).

systematic experimentation, we assessed the performance of both foundational classifiers—such as Logistic Regression, Decision Tree, SVM, and Naive Bayes—and advanced ensemble methods including Gradient Boosting, XGBoost, CatBoost, and AdaBoost.

Our results demonstrated that ensemble models significantly outperform traditional classifiers across multiple evaluation metrics, with CatBoost achieving the highest overall accuracy and Gradient Boosting producing the best KS statistic. The stacking ensemble, which combined multiple base learners, showed comparable performance to the best single model, reinforcing the value of ensemble learning for capturing diverse patterns in churn behavior.

Feature importance analysis revealed that contract type, tenure, and number of referrals are among the most influential predictors of churn. These findings can directly inform customer retention strategies by enabling targeted interventions for high-risk users.

While the current approach shows strong predictive performance, several opportunities remain for future exploration:

- **Temporal Modeling:** Incorporating time-series data, such as billing or usage trends over time, could improve model sensitivity to behavioral changes.
- **Explainability:** Applying tools like SHAP (SHapley Additive exPlanations) or LIME (Local Interpretable Model-agnostic Explanations) would offer more interpretable insights into individual churn predictions, which is especially valuable for stakeholder trust.
- **Cost-Sensitive Learning:** Future models could incorporate the economic cost of false positives and false negatives to optimize for business impact rather than pure accuracy.
- **Real-Time Scoring:** Deploying the model in a real-time environment to predict churn dynamically as new customer data becomes available would further enhance its practical utility.

Overall, this work highlights the effectiveness of machine learning—especially ensemble and stacking techniques—for customer churn prediction, and provides a foundation for future developments in data-driven retention strategies.

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The code and data used in this project are available at: <https://github.com/rajatrayaraddi/churn-prediction>

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